

INDIGENE AND SETTLER SYNDROME: A CHALLENGE TO NIGERIAN NATIONHOOD

By

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Abstract

Nigeria is a multi-ethnic and multi-religious country inhabited by sundry ethnic groups who are not only distinguished by language, customs and myth of origin, but also in size, power, and influence. The country is also marked by cultural, geographical and religious heterogeneity and above all by a long history of migration which makes virtually all Nigerians to be settlers. This indigene and settler syndrome is indeed a major problem in virtually all states of the federation even though, the level of violence related to the issue differs from state to state. However, as part of the efforts to cope with this problem and to accommodate differences in the true spirit of 'Unity in diversity', using a historical research method, this paper intends to dwell on finding the genesis of the problem, the constitutional provision on indigenship as well as providing a number of measures towards ending this problem which has become pandemic to the challenge of nationhood.

Introduction

Nigeria is a very highly complex, multi-ethnic, multi-lingual, multi-cultural and multi-religious polity. However, rather than nurture harmony and unity, these complex diversities tend to give rise to crises, such that conflicts have become common place in Nigeria which is usually about everything such as politics, economic control and competition after scarce resources, ethnicity and religion (Danfulani, 2005). Ellsworth (1999) observed that ethnicity and religious affiliation are the two highest identity

markers for a vast majority of Nigerians than other indices such as state, region and national identity. This is currently exhibited in a Nigeria in the growing tendency for crisis that emerged between those who are perceived as so called 'indigenes' and those who are regarded as 'settlers', and therefore, considered 'outsiders'.

It is pertinent to note that, policy makers have adopted a number of measures in order to curb the situation. A good example of such measure some scholars have argued created more

problems than it was intended to solve is Section 14 (3) of the 1979 Constitution which is parametria with section 14 (2) (FRN, 1999) captures the reasoning of Constitution Drafting Committee of 1976 which had reasoned that there was need to give every ethnic group in the country a sense of belonging. The Constitution provides thus: “The composition of the Government of the federation or any of its agencies and the conduct of its affairs shall be carried out in such a manner as to reflect the Federal Character of Nigeria, and the need to promote national unity and also to command loyalty, thereby ensuring that, there shall be no predominance of persons from few states or from few ethnic groups or other sectional groups in the government or any of its agencies”. This is the provisions in the constitution regarding the implementation of the federal character principle which in practice limits the existing opportunities to those defined as indigenes (Ibrahim, 2011).

Ibrahim (2011) further explained the consequence that millions of Nigerians who find themselves residents in places other than where they can claim indigeneity are labeled as strangers and settlers. Consequently, Nigerians so defined as settlers are subjected to all kind of exclusions and deprivations which differentiate them from the ‘natives’ and

members of the ‘host communities’. These practices often nurture lots of grievances among the people especially at the rural areas where these crises have serious negative consequences. However, these persistent problems that have continued to be an engaging conundrum in our effort towards attaining the goals of one nation, built in freedom, peace and unity have occupied the attention of all serious-minded Nigerians. Therefore, against this background, the paper tries to delve into finding the genesis of the problem, the constitutional provision on citizenship and indigeneship as well as providing a number of measures towards ending the problem. Thus, the paper is divided into six sections. Section one covers the general introduction; section two handles conceptual clarification; section three deals with theoretical framework; section four looks at the indigene-settler phenomenon in Nigeria, its causes and implications; section five deals with the constitutional provision on citizenship; while section six handles conclusion and recommendations.

Conceptual Clarification

Citizenship: Citizenship according to Gauba (2003) is the status of an individual as a full and responsible member of a political community. He further states that citizenship is the product of a community

where the right to rule is decided by a prescribed procedure which expresses the will of the general body of its members. While ascertaining their will, nobody is discriminated on grounds of race, religion, gender, place of birth (Gaub, 2003).

Thus, citizenship is a relationship between the individual and the state in which both are linked by reciprocal rights and duties (Ifesinachi, 2010). Citizenship in the modern state seems to proceed from the continuum of individualism and communalism. Liberal citizenship advances the principle of 'citizenship right' and places particular stress on private entitlement and the status of the individual as an autonomous actor (Heywood cited in Ifesinachi, 2010). Marshall in Egwu, (2009) further explains that it is much easier to define citizenship as a status bestowed on those who are full members of a community. For him, call those who possess the status of citizens are equal with respect to the rights and duties with which the status is endowed".

Following from the above, one could decipher major problems associated with citizenship related issues in Nigeria. This is because it appears increasingly difficult to determine who is a full member of a particular environment in Nigeria especially when the major variable in determining the tied to land

ownership, which, in most places is reinforced by the indigene/settler crisis.

Indigene and Settler: An attempt to conceptually define an 'indigene' and a 'settler' is surrounded with contradiction in the Nigerian context because of the difficulty in delineating an indigene from a settler, since virtually all ethnic groups are known to have migrated from somewhere (Best, 2005). However, if to consider the concept of indigeneship for instance, it has been acknowledged that the idea of "indigeneity" is universally problematic because it draws on the perception of groups of people who first settled in an area where the land and other opportunities belong to them. But because of the inevitable migration of people to an area already inhabited, the earliest settlers are often threatened by the new arrivals especially when competition over economic resources ensues. This scenario can make conflict inevitable (Best, 2005).

Theoretical Framework

Social identity theory is used in analyzing this work. The theory is rooted in the works of Emile Durkhiem and Williams McDougall. It was formally developed by Henri Tajfel and John Turner in 1979 to understand the psychological basis of intergroup discrimination. It also attempted to identify the minimal

conditions that would lead members of one group to discriminate in favour of the in-group to which they belonged and against another out-group (Haslam, 2001). The theory argues that group membership creates in-group/self-categorisation and enhancement in ways that favour the in-group at the expense of the out-group (Haslam, 2001). Turner (1982) shows that, the mere act of individuals categorizing themselves as group members was sufficient to lead them to display in-group membership. The theory also identifies three variables that contribute to the emergence of in-group favouritism. Such variables include:-

- The extent to which individuals identify with an in-group to internalize such group membership as an aspect of their self-concept.
- The extent to which the prevailing context provides ground for comparison between groups.
- The perceived relevance of the comparison group which itself will be shaped by the relative and absolute status of the in-group.

Therefore, individuals are likely to display favouritism when an in-group is central to their self-definition and a giving comparison is meaningful if the outcome is contestable.

However, some argued that the theory has become so broad that it ceases to be falsifiable as virtually any experimental outcome can be interpreted within its overarching framework (Hogg and Williams, 2000). Despite its broad influence, the social identity theory has not been without its critics. Such criticism is that with its focus on individual processes and social cognition. The theory also suffers from some of the flaws it points out in others; namely being too reductionist and individualistic (Farr, 1999).

Nevertheless, in spite of the criticism, the emergence of the theory has played a critical role in the resuscitation of interest in group processes both within and outside social psychology and ultimately rests on simple, elegant, testable and usable principle. In other words, social identity theory has a considerable impact on social psychology. It is tested in a wide range of field and settings and includes prejudice, stereotyping, negotiation and language use. The theory also has implications on the way people deal with social and organizational change. In essence therefore, the theory is very relevant to this study especially when one considered the level at which Nigerians sees themselves as belonging to different ethnic groups and not belonging to one single nationality.

Indigene/Settler Trend in Nigeria

The question concerning who “indigenes” or “settlers” are is within the ambit of identity. This is a domain of exclusion and permanent contestation. This is so because the distinction between these groups is used as a way of excluding people: “Indigenes” seek the exclusion of those categorised as “settlers”, while those being excluded on the ground of “settlement” seek equity and contest their exclusion on grounds of citizenship of the Nigerian State (Egwu, 2005).

The concept of “settler”, particularly in the Nigeria sense of the word, breeds serious problems. Although a settler may be thought of in terms of a person who does not live in his/her original place of birth, or his/her ancestral home, for reasons ranging from business, war and work, what makes this movement and settlement problematic is the tendency for the “local” people to discriminate these “newcomers”. As mentioned above, different discriminatory terms are used by the so-called natives in their local dialect to describe the migrant people even if they have settled in the place for a long period. The migrants are also denied scholarship awards and employment in local and state institutions where they reside. This overly creates an alien psyche and sets the “settlers” against the “natives” or “indigenes”. It makes the ‘settlers’ raise

questions on their status as Nigerian citizens. For instance, how long should one reside in another part of Nigeria to be treated equal to other persons in the community? Why should someone be called a “settler” in his/her country while others ascribe themselves the status of “indigene” with accrued privileges? These issues underscore the persistence of the citizenship question in Nigeria today. Best (2005) attempts to explain conflicts arising from the indigene-settler divide. Best’s argument is that the majority ethnic groups, that are more mobile, are inclined to overshadow the minority ethnic groups in their own lands. He cites the impact of the Tiv, who are a majority group in North-Central Nigeria, over the Jukun in Wukari and the Hausa/Fulani over the Kataf in Zangon Kataf as cases in point. However, it can be underlined, in contradiction to Best’s position, that in a place like Kano, even though the Ibo and Yoruba groups are national majority groups, they are in minority in the Hausa-dominated Kano city. Thus, there have been conflicts along the indigene-settler divide between these three groups in the city. So, the point is not the question of dominance of one group by another because of the superiority of its population. Rather a more plausible explanation lies in the failure of the Nigerian state to web its numerous ethnic

nationalities through the conscious creation of a national structure that will enhance equal rights and justice and access to social welfare for all individuals and groups (Best, 2005).

Therefore, the indigene – settler dichotomy, which is a nationwide phenomenon, has largely acquired vast acceptability in Nigeria, and the concept of “indigeneship” also remains very strong and viable, as social spaces, even cities, are identified as “belonging to” particular ethnic groups. As Plotnicov (1972) notes, “Owners of the land” is a phrase widely employed in Nigeria to designate the indigenous peoples of an area, even when they are politically subordinate there; while “Strangers” [settlers], the paired contrasting term, covers people of alien origin who are permanently settled among these indigenous people. An attempt to clarify any of the two concepts, however, implies a simultaneous engagement with the other. Mamdani (1998) aptly captures this relationship: “The settler – native question is a political question. It is also a historical question. Settlers and natives belong together. You cannot have one without the other for it is the relationship between them that makes one a settler and the other a native”.

Causes of the Indigene-Settler Crises in Nigeria Land Ownership

In Nigeria, indigeneity is associated with land ownership. This is not only limited to Nigeria, land ownership is an issue all over Africa. As such, anything that affects the land affects the people and must be resisted by all means. Eme Awa (1985) supports this view when he asserted that indigeneity is strong in Nigeria because people are seeing the land as a primary form of property in the traditional society and its source as a form of wealth (Awa, 1985). This account for the deep-rooted animosity between the indigenes (land owners) and the settlers in Nigeria. The desire of the settlers to have access to the land at the expense of the indigenes is the major problem in virtually all states of the federation. Take the Kuteb/Chamba conflict for example. Although a number of ethnic groups such as Hausa, Jukun, Kuteb and Chamba are found in the Takum area, the major contest has been between the Kuteb and Chamba. From the available historical evidence, both Kuteb and Chamba had taken effective residency of the area around Takum prior to the colonial intervention. However, in the present context of contestation over the “ownership” of Takum, each of the two communal groups has resorted to different accounts of history to bolster its claim (Ibrahim, 2011)

Political Patronage/ Competition

One of the major factors that triggered the indigene/ settler crisis is political exclusion. The return to civil rule in 1999 saw the indigenous people using their population to their advantage by voting massively for indigenes while settlers are finding it very difficult to occupy position of authority as a result of their minority status. Therefore, the opening up of political space under civilian rule has been accompanied by intense ethnic competition at all levels of government. The indigenous elite have consolidated their power and control of the state, excluding the settlers particularly on the basis of religion and ethnicity (Higizi, 2011). For example, the crisis in Ife/Modakeke is fuelled by these dynamics despite the fact that it pitches one sub-Yoruba group against another. The reason for the conflict between the two communities seems to have been generated by disagreements over the creation of new local government areas. It goes to show that the question of access to local power is at the core of the unending conflict between the two communities (Ibrahim, 2011)

The Nature and Character of Nigerian State

Karl Marx definition of the state as the executive committee for managing the

affairs of the bourgeoisie explains the recurrent crises of indigenes and settlers since the centre is conceived as the chief producer and distributor of economic resources. Jega (2002) outlined three distinguishing characteristics of the Nigerian state; *rent seeking, prebendalism and patrimony*. To situate the phenomenon properly, it is necessary to point out that the current central paradigm of Nigerian politics allows the state to have dominating and unchallenged sole distributive clearing power for economic and political spoils and as such, Mohammed, (2005) avers that the enormous resources at the disposal of the state accruing from the sale of petroleum resources has led to the intense competition for power leading to the widespread use of money and armed thugs. The state as the avenue for the control of decision-making apparatus of political spoils and economic patronage raise the competition to the level of vicious struggle.

Politically, since the Nigerian state is seen as a rentier state and the centre as the distributive point and centre of primitive accumulation, politicians instigate ethnic and primordial sentiments in order to achieve their selfish ends. For instance, the ability of a state to capture and retain the affective attachment of its citizens depends to a large extent on how

fair and equitable it distributes public goods especially in a society as Nigeria, that is characterized by pronounced segmental cleavages. Lack of equity and fairness in the distribution or allocation of values can easily deconstruct such a plural community into competing primordial identities like ethno-regional platform such as Afenifere, Ohaneze Ndigbo and Arewa Consultative Forum as well as religious platforms such as Jama'atu Nasril Islam (JNI), Christain Association of Nigeria (CAN) etc. all competing for space and resources in the polity. (Gambo, 2011).

The Problem of Nigerian Constitution

Nigerian citizens are facing undue deprivation within the country particularly in an area which is not his/ her indigenous place. This is contrary to Section 42 (2) of the 1999 constitution that says no citizen of the country shall be subjected to any disability or deprivation merely by reason of the circumstances of his birth. (FRN 1999). The non-indigenes in any part of the country are subjected to undue frustration, oppression, marginalisation etc. the interesting thing about this is that, it is not limited to a particular area.

For example, those that are currently undergoing this experience will do worse to other non- indigenes in their own area if they have the opportunity.

Non-indigenes are discriminated against in Nigeria federal state. This is the root of the crisis associated with indigene- settler in the country. As a result of the crisis generated by the indigene- settler issue in the country, the concept of the Nigerian state does not really hold any appeal to the average Nigerian. Nigerian people are more loyal and believe more in their various ethnic or indigenous groups. As a result, they hold more allegiance to these ethnic groups. This perhaps account for the dimension ethnic crisis is assuming in the country. For instance, one part of Jos is predominantly occupied by Hausa/Fulani who are mainly Muslims and another part is occupied by Christians. The boundary between these two settlements is so rigidly defined that there is hardly any interaction between them (Gambo, 2011).

Implications

The implication of all the cases of conflicts arising from indigene-settler disputes highlighted above is that the citizenship question in Nigeria remains contentious and a veritable trigger of social upheavals. It is apparent that Nigerians residing in parts of the country other than their own feel less at home because of the *de facto* practices of the so-called indigenes or natives which tend to alienate the 'visitors'. Many Nigerians

suffer from discrimination and are denied certain rights where they live because their host communities see them as settlers and non-indigenes (Toure, 2009).

Paradoxically the *Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999* in Section 42 abhors discrimination of Nigerians by virtue of their ethnic affiliation, sex, religion etc. The Constitution clearly states in its fourth chapter the rights of the Nigerian citizens. It however fails to clarify the definition of what a citizen is and their rights according to which state of the federation he or she lives. This ambiguity in the 1999 Constitution is responsible for some of these inter and intra-ethnic conflicts that Nigeria has witnessed since the 1990s (Nnoli, 2003).

Constitutional Provision on Citizenship

In the nation's 1979 constitution, the phrase "belongs or belonged to a community indigenous of Nigeria" was used in the definition of citizenship Section 23, Sub section (1) (a)] while the phrase "federal character" also entered Nigeria constitution in 1979 to denote a principle of minority group inclusion in federal government and its affairs (Ostien, 2009). Section 147 (3) of the 1999 constitution also states that "...the President shall appoint at least one minister from each state, who shall be an

indigene of such a state" (CFRN 1999). Thus the 1999 constitution recognizes that there are indigenes in Nigeria. Ordinarily, one would have thought the crisis on the notion of citizenship would have been put to rest by the constitutional provision of Section 25 (1a) of CFRN, 1999 that defined citizenship in Nigeria as;

Every person born in Nigeria on or before the date of independence, either of whose parents or any of whose grandparents belongs or belonged to community indigenous to Nigeria

The seeming retention of both the concepts of indigeneship and federal character to protect minority interests does not abate their fears. Danfulani (2005) opines that the federal character in Nigeria refers to distinctive desire of the people of Nigeria to promote national unity, foster national loyalty and give every citizen of Nigeria a sense of belonging in the nation irrespective of where they find themselves. Section 14 (4) of the Constitution states similar condition for the states and the local governments, it recognizes the multi-ethnic and multi-religious nature of Nigeria as well as other social diversities and enjoined decision makers to recognize the diversity of the people within its area of authority to ensure proportionate and equitable

representation of all persons in government. Of course, it is for these reasons such as to ensure and engineer social equity as well as to deliberately provide opportunities to disadvantaged group (minority) in order to give them the needed sense of belonging wherever they find themselves that this principle of representation is expected to extend to bureaucratic, economic and political posts at all levels of government. But again, the question is why there should be a disadvantaged mainly on the basis of ethnicity, when the right conferred on the citizens is predicted on having a sense of belongings to the fatherland.

Conclusion

The paper has examined the issue of indigene- settler and the problem associated with it in Nigeria. It is observed that contrary to constitutional provisions that all citizens are equal regardless of colour, ethnic origin, sex, religion etc but in practice, the equality of Nigerians is not real. The contradictions in the nation's constitution led to this. However, the indigene- settler crisis is aggravated by so many factors such as land issue, political patronage/ competition, constitutional problems among others. It appears that governments at various levels lack the required political will to once and for all tackle the problem. Many panels and

commissions were set up to unearth the causes of the crisis. Despite the thorough jobs done by these bodies, governments lack the courage to implement the recommendations.

Recommendations:

Since the 'indigene - settler problem' in Nigeria is an issue that must be confronted head-on, it is imperative that government, and indeed the non-governmental sector, pay adequate attention to issues of ethnicity and ethnic studies in the country. It is also imperative to redefine the status and character of the Nigerian citizenship.

First, there is a need to address the issue of citizenship rights constitutionally. This can be done through a constitutional amendment that should clearly state that Nigerians have inalienable rights of residence, to contest for public office, own land, have access to social benefits such as employment and scholarship in any part of the country.

Secondly the treatment of any Nigerian by any local and state authorities should be based on justice and fairness. This will douse tension among the diverse ethnic groups that are spatially distributed in almost all the towns and cities of the country. In this way, Nigerians will mould a spirit of accommodation among themselves thereby fostering the much-

needed national integration and cohesion for development to take place.

Thirdly, it is equally important for Nigeria, in its drive towards inclusive citizenship to consent to the role of Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Community-Based Organizations (CBOs), and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) that are involved in civil rights campaigns. These organizations should advocate at the various levels of government for the rights of Nigerians as individuals and groups to be recognised.

Fourthly, a government agency like the National Orientation Agency (NOA) should put forward more aggressive strategies to entrench a psyche of nationalism in the citizenry. This way, Nigerians will imbibe the culture of love for their country and love for fellow Nigerians; these are germane if Nigeria is to follow the path to national unity and development.

Fifthly, the land issue also must be addressed. Land reforms are overdue and as such must be undertaken. The reforms must make land a resource that is accessible to all. A situation where some Nigerians are denied access to land because they are perceived to be 'visitors', 'new-comers', 'non-indigenes' or 'migrants' will only tear the country apart rather than web Nigerians together. This is

where the roles of community heads and traditional rulers become relevant. They can enhance harmony amongst Nigerians through peaceful resolution of interpersonal disputes, getting their subjects to understand Nigeria's diversities and the need to accommodate other Nigerians despite differences (Aluiagba, 2008).

Lastly, the followers should be taught to respect the cultures of others and to see the humanness in other Nigerians. This will incorporate rather than alienate the vast number of Nigerians who reside in other parts of the country thereby providing a soothing relief to the apprehension created by contestations.

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